

Four-part Harmonization Using Probabilistic Models: Comparison of Models With and Without Chord Nodes

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we explore machine learning models that generate four-part harmonies according to the melody of a soprano voice. Although researchers have already tried to produce four-part harmonization through machine learning, the computational models that most studies have proposed already contain nodes or states that represent chords or harmonic functions. Explicitly introducing such nodes or states is suitable from the viewpoint of practically achieving musically acceptable harmonization, but it is unsuitable from the scientific viewpoint of acquiring the fundamental concepts of harmonies from actual music data. Therefore, we developed two kinds of computational models, one that contains chord nodes and another does not, and investigate to what extent the model without chord nodes acquires the fundamental concept of harmonies compared to the model with chord nodes. For our models, we describe musical simultaneity (i.e., the appropriateness of combinations of simultaneously played notes) and musical sequentiality (i.e., the smoothness of the melodic line within each voice) are described as dependencies between random variables in Bayesian networks. Both models learned 254 pieces taken from a Hymn corpus, and the results of this experiment show that the Bayesian network without chord nodes acquired some of the basic rules of harmony.

1. INTRODUCTION

Automatic music harmonization is an important subtask in automatic music arrangement. In general, this task is divided into two types of harmonization. The first type is a sequence of chord symbols, such as C-F-G7-C, a given melody [1–3]. The second type comprises concrete notes to voices other than the melody voice. The typical form in the latter type of harmonization is a four-part harmony, that consists of soprano, alto, tenor, and bass voices. The four-part harmonization is a traditional part of the theoretical education of Western classical musicians, so numerous researchers have attempted to generate automatically the four-part harmonization [4–10].

One of the most commonly used approaches is to develop an expert system (rule-based system) [4]. Ebcioglu, for example, implemented the knowledge of harmonization by

using a logic programming language called BSL [4]. A rule-based harmonization system is difficult to develop, because this system's rules are various and hence often difficult to integrate without contradiction. For example, two note allocation rules include one rule that considers consonance between the voices and another rule that considers the natural temporal connection within the voice. Given that these rules make different considerations, they might recommend different notes, in which case meta rules for resolving such contradictions are necessary. However, developing such rules is not easy. Some studies have attempted to achieve harmonization as a constraint satisfaction problem or with the genetic algorithm, instead of directly implementing note allocation rules. Researchers designed these constraints or fitness functions, according to basic some rules of harmonization [6, 7].

In recent years, the number of studies on four-part harmonization that use machine learning technologies has been increasing [5, 8, 9], thus increasing the difficulty of designing meta-rules. The scientific interest in these studies is to discover the principle of harmony from actual music data so that humans do not necessarily need to implement it on a computer. For example, Hild et al. developed a J. S. Bach-style choral harmonization system using several neural networks [5], Allan and Williams proposed a four-part harmonization method based on a hidden Markov model (HMM) [8], and Yi and Goldsmith proposed a four-part harmonization method based on a Markov decision process [9].

Researchers strive to address two issues while developing a computational model for four-part harmonization. The first issue is to take into account the simultaneity and sequentiality of harmonization. The simultaneity is the appropriate (e.g., non-dissonant) allocation of notes that are simultaneously sounding, while sequentiality is the smooth connection in a melodic line within each voice. The second issue is to take a limited number of training data into account. Because four-part harmonization has very complex dependencies both within and between voices, the model should describe all of the dependencies. As the complexity of the model increases, however, the number of training data required will exponentially increase. The quantity of available training data should therefore be considered while designing the model.

In Yi and Goldsmith's model [9], a state is defined as a 10-tuple $(S_1, A_1, T_1, B_1, S_2, A_2, T_2, B_2, S_3, P)$, where S_i, A_i, T_i, B_i are respectively the soprano, alto, tenor, and bass notes at time i , and P is a temporal position. The

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temporal sequence of such states is treated as a Markov decision process. This model has the potential of generating four-part harmony, because it considers both simultaneity and sequentiality. Unfortunately, it usually requires a tremendous amount of training data precisely because it has many states. Not surprisingly, Yi and Goldsmith do not report the results of learning with an actual corpus.

Hild et al. attempted four-part harmonization by integrating three kinds of neural networks [5], one that generates a sequence of harmonic functions called harmonic skeletons from a soprano melody, a second one that allocates concrete notes from the harmonic skeletons, and a third one that inserts eighth notes for ornamentation. They trained their neural networks separately on one set of Bach chorales in major key and another set in minor key, each set containing 20 chorales.

Allan and Williams used a hidden Markov model (HMM) [8]. This model's has hidden states represent chords that are designed to emit an observable melody line. The states are coded as a list of pitch intervals of the alto, tenor, and bass notes from the soprano note, such as 0:4:9:16 / T (T stands for tonic). This model takes into account simultaneity and sequentiality, but this model also requires a lot of training data due to its large number of states. In fact, Allan and Williams model distinguishes each unique voicing of the same chord.

Buyss and Merwe adopted a weighted finite-state transducer (WFST) for four-part harmonization [10]. Their WFST consists of three graphical models for estimating chords, bass notes, and inner-voice(i.e., alto and tenor) notes. The alto, tenor, and bass notes are coded in separate nodes unlike the above-mentioned models.

Most of the above-mentioned studies introduced nodes or states that represent chords (e.g., C, G) or harmonic functions (e.g., tonic). In contrast, the present study introduces a computational model that does not explicitly contain the concept of harmony so that the researchers could investigate whether this model is able to acquire the concepts of harmony from actual music data. Specifically, we developed a computational model of four-part harmonization with and without chord nodes to investigate to what extent the model without chord nodes learns the harmony that the model with chord nodes was already programmed to know. For our computational model, we adopt a Bayesian network, because most of the existing methods can be generalized to Bayesian networks.

2. PROPOSED METHOD

In this section, we present our method of four-part harmonization that uses a Bayesian network.

2.1 Problem Statement

The problem that we aim to solve is how to generate melodic lines for the alto, tenor, and bass voices, according to the existing melody of the soprano voice. Based on the typical form of Chant Donne used in the theoretical education of harmony, we assume that the rhythm of all of the voices is the same, in other words, the number of notes and the

onset and offset times for each note are the same for all of the voices.

2.2 Overview of the Procedure

The user provides the system with a melody in the MIDI format. Let S_1, \dots, S_N be the note numbers of the notes in the given melody. Then, the system determines the notes of the remaining voices (alto, tenor, and bass). Let A_i, T_i, B_i be the i -th notes of the alto, tenor, and bass voices, respectively. The i -th notes A_i, T_i, B_i are inferred after the previous notes $A_{i-1}, T_{i-1}, B_{i-1}$ are determined, and this process is repeatedly performed until the last notes are inferred. Finally, the result is output in the MIDI format.

2.3 Design of Bayesian Networks

Figure 1. Chord model

Figure 2. Non-chord model

The Bayesian networks that we designed for this experiment appear in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 2 shows a model that does not include chord nodes (called a non-chord model), while Figure 1 shows a model that includes chord nodes (called a chord model). S_i, A_i, T_i, B_i, C_i represent the note numbers of the i -th note in the soprano, alto, tenor, and bass part, and their ranges are [60, 81], [55, 76], [48, 69], and [41, 62], respectively. C_i represents the chord name for i -th note and takes an element of $\{C, C\#, \dots, B\} \times \{\text{maj}, \text{min}\}$. To all nodes, we introduced a special symbol "0", which means no notes or chords. When the first note and chord is inferred, there are no notes or chords for time $i - 1$. The symbol "0" is set to the nodes $S_{i-1}, A_{i-1}, T_{i-1}, B_{i-1}, C_{i-1}$. Similarly, this symbol is set to the nodes $S_{i+1}, A_{i+1}, T_{i+1}, B_{i+1}, C_{i+1}$ when the last note and chord is inferred.

The common feature of these Bayesian networks is that they include nodes for the $(i + 1)$ -th note as well as nodes for the i -th note. While the i -th note is being inferred, the $(i + 1)$ -th note is also inferred at the same time. Because the likelihoods of all nodes are taken into account, we avoided the values for the i -th note that would decrease the likelihood of the $(i + 1)$ -th note. Thus, we have taken into account the sequentiality from the previous note to the next note.

There is a difference in the network design towards simultaneity between our two Bayesian networks. For the non-chord model, we assumed that the note for each voice depends on the note in the soprano voice. Ideally, all pairs of the nodes S_i, A_i, T_i, B_i should have arcs because all

voices are mutually dependent. However, taking dependencies into account is difficult in practice, because a large amount of training data is required. We therefore simplified the dependencies between the voices. In the chord model, the note for each voice is assumed to depend on the chord. Ideally, the dependencies between the voices should be taken into account. It is also practically difficult to take dependencies into account in the non-chord model, due to a limited amount of training data.

The conditional probability tables (CPTs) were trained with a corpus. The details of the training are described in Section 3.1.

3. EXPERIMENTS

We conducted experiments on the generation of four-part harmonies using the two above-mentioned Bayesian networks and compared the results.

3.1 Learning CPTs

For the learning CPTs of the Bayesian networks, we constructed a melody corpus consisting of 254 four-part melodies that we took from a book of hymns [11]. We limited the hymns to major-key pieces in which the shortest notes are eighth notes. We then manually input the scores of the selected pieces, and Band-in-a-Box [13] automatically labeled the chord for each note.

Because we wanted to assume that the rhythms of the four voices are completely the same (i.e., the onset and offset times of four voices are the same), we had to modify the training data so that the data satisfied this condition. We therefore divided all notes that were longer than eighth notes into a sequence of eighth notes with the same pitch. The CPTs were trained with the data modified in this manner. By introducing this modification, however, the probability that each note is the same as the previous note artificially high, so we assigned a penalty coefficient (currently 0.2) to these probabilities.

3.2 Experimental condition

We used 32 soprano melodies [12] in the C-major key for the inputs of the four-part harmonization. After generating four-part harmonies for these 32 soprano melodies with the chord and non-chord models, we compared the results through the following criteria:

C1 The number of notes containing dissonance intervals.

The dissonance intervals are defined as minor 2nd, major 2nd, diminished 5th, minor 7th, and major 7th. The notes forming the G7 chord (e.g., Soprano: D, Alto: F, Tenor: B, Bass: G) were excluded even if they contained dissonance intervals. Because the relations of chords and notes are explicitly trained in the chord model, the number of notes containing dissonance intervals in the chord model would be less than that in the non-chord model.

C2 The number of non-diatonic notes.

The melodies used here are actually used for excises of harmonics at music colleges, so the melodies are orthodox

and hence the results of harmonization should not contain non-diatonic notes. This number ended up being close to zero, so this result fit the criterion better than did the other results for their respective criteria.

C3 Whether the last chord is C.

All of the melodies used here should end with the C chord. If the results of the non-chord model meet this criterion, then we can conclude that this model appropriately acquired one of the important rules in harmonics: ending with the tonic chord. The results of the chord model, on the other hand, would easily meet this criterion because it was directly trained in the sequentiality of chord symbols.

C4 The number of notes containing the same note name in more than three voices.

Allocating the same note name to simultaneous notes in different voices (e.g., soprano: C, alto: C, tenor: E, bass: C) does not cause dissonance but rather does make the music monotonous. Such note allocation should therefore be avoided.

C5 The number of successive large (more than perfect 4th) note motions in the bass voice.

Successive, large note motions will decrease the smoothness in a sequence of notes within a voice. In particular, successive large note motions in the bass part should be avoided, because the conventional job of the bass voice is to keep the piece grounded. To avoid successive large note motions in the chord model, the model should train in chord inversions and infer appropriate inversions given the previous and/or next notes. If the model does not learn chord inversions sufficiently, then it would output the root note of each chord for the bass part, decreasing the sequential smoothness.

C6 The number of note names appearing in each voice.

When only two or three note names appear in a certain voice, the music is monotonous. This number should therefore not be low (e.g., less than three).

3.3 Experimental results

Table 1 lists the results of evaluation based on the above-mentioned criteria.

Concerning the dissonance of the output harmonies, 3% of all chords for the chord model and 18% of all chords for the non-chord model were dissonant. Because the chord model was directly trained in the relations between chords and notes, it successfully selected chord tones as long as it inferred an appropriate chord. Accordingly, this model generated harmonies with almost no dissonance. On the other hand, the results for the non-chord model feature more dissonant chords than do the results of the chord model, because the latter model was trained only in the relationship between the soprano voice and the other voices. However, we can conclude that the non-chord model acquired a basis of harmony to some extent, even though it

Table 1. Evaluation results (C: the chord model, N: the non-chord model; ○: satisfactory, ×: unsatisfactory). “Total” for C6 is averages, not summations.

	Total # of Note	C1		C2		C3		C4		C5					C6									
		C	N	C	N	C	N	C	N	C				N										
		2	3	4	5+	2	3	4	5+	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Alto	Tenor	Bass	Alto	Tenor	Bass						
Sample 1	15	1	1	0	0	○	○	8	3	2	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	2	3	4	3	6
Sample 2	14	0	4	0	0	○	○	5	4	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	2	3	4	5	5	4	
Sample 3	14	0	1	0	0	○	○	7	4	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	3	4	6	6	
Sample 4	15	1	0	0	0	○	○	5	3	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	4	3	4	3	4	
Sample 5	14	1	3	0	0	○	○	6	3	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	2	2	3	4	5	6	
Sample 6	14	2	2	0	0	○	○	6	5	2	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	2	2	3	5	3	5	
Sample 7	14	1	0	0	0	○	○	4	5	2	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	2	2	4	3	5	
Sample 8	13	0	2	0	0	○	○	6	2	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	3	3	4	4	5	
Sample 9	13	1	2	0	0	○	○	7	2	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	2	1	2	3	5	4	
Sample 10	15	0	2	0	0	○	○	7	5	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	4	3	5	3	5	
Sample 11	15	1	3	0	0	○	○	6	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	3	5	5	5	
Sample 12	13	0	1	0	0	○	○	5	7	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	2	2	3	5	3	4	
Sample 13	14	0	3	0	1	○	○	4	2	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	2	4	3	5	6	4	
Sample 14	14	0	5	0	0	○	×	7	3	1	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	2	2	3	4	6	6	
Sample 15	14	0	1	0	0	○	×	7	4	1	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	2	2	3	4	5	7	
Sample 16	14	2	4	0	0	○	○	2	4	3	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	4	3	4	4	5	
Sample 17	14	0	6	0	1	○	○	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	4	4	6	4	
Sample 18	13	2	2	0	1	○	○	5	5	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	2	2	3	6	6	4	
Sample 19	14	0	1	0	0	○	○	3	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	4	4	3	4	
Sample 20	14	0	1	0	0	○	○	6	6	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	2	4	3	5	3	5	
Sample 21	14	0	5	0	0	○	○	3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	2	4	3	4	4	5	
Sample 22	14	0	3	0	0	○	○	4	3	0	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	2	3	3	3	3	4	
Sample 23	14	0	5	0	0	○	○	4	5	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	3	4	7	7	
Sample 24	14	1	1	0	0	○	○	6	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	3	4	5	4	4	
Sample 25	14	1	0	0	0	○	○	3	3	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	4	3	5	4	5	
Sample 26	14	2	1	0	0	○	○	3	4	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	4	3	6	6	6	
Sample 27	14	0	5	0	1	○	○	5	3	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	4	4	4	7	5	
Sample 28	14	0	5	0	1	○	○	5	4	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	3	4	4	7	4	
Sample 29	14	1	1	0	0	○	○	5	4	4	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	1	3	3	3	4	
Sample 30	14	0	3	0	0	○	○	4	3	1	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	2	4	3	3	3	5	
Sample 31	11	0	3	0	1	○	○	4	3	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	2	2	4	2	5	4	
Sample 32	14	0	3	0	1	○	○	7	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	2	4	3	3	4	
Total	445	17	79	0	7	32	30	164	111	30	12	8	21	24	18	8	1	2	2.7	3.1	4.1	4.4	4.8	

was not directly told the chord symbols, because less than 20% of its chords were dissonant. Most dissonant intervals appeared between voices in which the arcs are omitted (e.g, alto and tenor, alto and bass) due to a computational cost. Ideally, these arcs should be added but adding arcs exponentially increase the computational cost (in fact, a conventional PC needs more than 40 minutes to harmonize four-measure melodies, even though the present model takes only a few seconds). Given that the voices connecting to each other with arcs did not cause dissonant intervals in the non-chord model, we expect that the model’s dissonant intervals would decrease if we were to add arcs to it.

The results of the chord model include no non-diatonic notes, and the non-chord model employed only a few non-diatonic notes. These results mean that both models were trained in the typical usage of notes in the C-major key. Out of the seven non-diatonic notes that the non-chord model selected, two were F# notes forming a sequence of E-F#-

G and one was an F# note forming a sequence of G-F#-G together with the previous and next notes. The former F# note can be interpreted as a passing note and the later F# note can be interpreted as an auxiliary note.

All pieces written by the chord model and 97% of the pieces by the non-chord model ends with the chord of C major, meaning that both models knew a basic rule of harmony, which is to end with the tonic chord. In all three pieces that did not end with C major from the non-chord model, the bass part ended with A, which technically made the last chord Am. Ending with Am instead of C after G7 in the C-major key is known as a deceptive cadence and is often used in realistic music. Therefore these results are not necessarily inappropriate.

In the chord model, 37% of all chords contained the same note name in more than three voices (e.g, C-G-C-C), while only 24% did in the non-chord model. These results arose because the chord model does not consider the relation

between voices. It may be improved by adding arcs between voices, but the network would become more complex, making it difficult to train with a limited amount of data.

The results for the chord model contained many successive, large (perfect 4th or more) note motions compared to the non-chord model, because the chord models simultaneous nodes for the chord (C_i) and bass (B_i) have a greater dependency than do its successive bass nodes (B_{i+1}, B_i, B_{i+1}).

The number of different note names appearing in each voice is between 2 and 4 for the chord model and higher than 4 on average for the non-chord model. In fact, some of the chord models outputs for the alto and tenor voices were monotonous repetitions of only a few notes, while the non-chord model smoothly connected notes within each voice.

3.4 Discussion

Figure 3. Sample 25 with the chord model

Figure 4. Sample 25 with the non-chord model

Figure 4 shows the result of Sample 25 for the non-chord model. This result has the following chord progression:

| C F F Em | Dm C G7 | C F C/E F | C/E G7 C/E |

From the fact that no voices have non-chord tones in this progression, we can deduce that this model successfully learned the chord tones of frequently used chords even though it was not given chord symbols during the training phase. In addition, the chord progression was based on functional harmony such as:

C (tonic) → F (subdominant) → Em (tonic counter parallel),

Dm (subdominant parallel) → C (tonic) → G7 (dominant).

In particular, the chord progression ends with a typical cadence, C → F → C → G7 → C. Using G7 instead of G as a previous chord of C was suitable because the tritone pushes towards a resolution. The bass line basically consists of conjunct motions and motions of 5th and therefore is a musically orthodox bass line; however, the bass note for the last C chord was E when it should have been C.

Table 2. Typical cadences generated with the non-chord model

Samples	Cadences		
Sample 1, 6, 9	F	Bm(-5)/D	C
Sample 2, 7, 10, 18, 28	C	Bm(-5)/D	C
Sample 3	Am	G	C
Sample 4, 16, 19, 29, 31	G7	G7	C
Sample 5, 8, 11, 13, 22	C	G7	C
Sample 20	C	F	C
Sample 23, 27	C	G/D	C
Sample 26	C/G	G7	C

Many other pieces also generated typical cadences. Examples are listed in Table 2. All of these cadences are commonly used in realistic music, so we consider our model to have learned most of the commonly used cadences.

The result of Sample 25 for the chord model is shown in Figure 3. The inferred chord progression consists of only three chords, C, F, and G, and this makes the harmony monotonous; however the actual chords are slightly different because the third note for the tenor voice is G instead of A and the fifth note for the alto voice is B instead of C. Every bass note is the root of the chord, and this makes the harmony more monotonous.

Figure 5. Sample 29 with the chord model

Figure 6. Sample 29 with the non-chord model

Figure 6 shows the result of Sample 29 for the non-chord model, which has an orthodox chord progression of ending the former half with G7 and the latter half with C. In successive G7 chords, the tenor note was D whether the soprano note was B, and vice versa. Taking different notes for the soprano and tenor voices avoided a monotonous harmony. The principal difference from the result for the chord model (Figure 7) was the chord progression in the third measure: | C F Bm(-5)/D C |. The result for the chord model includes only two chords, C and G, making the harmony very monotonous. Every note in the alto voice was C or B, and every note in the tenor voice was G. These are also reasons why the harmony is monotonous.

Next, we present an example of the non-chord model not generating a typical cadence (Figure 8). This piece ends with a deceptive cadence: | C G/B Am7 |. In addition, some chords sounded dissonant due to major 2nd or minor 2nd intervals between the tenor and bass voices. The chord model (Figure 7) produced no dissonant chords, but the harmony was monotonous similar to Sample 25 (Figure 4), because every chord was C, F, or G and because almost every bass note was the root of the chord.

To summarize, the non-chord model successfully achieved smooth harmonies by using various diatonic chords and in created a smooth bass line consisting mainly of conjunct motions and motions of 5th. In addition, the non-chord model generated typical and appropriate cadences in most pieces. The chord model generated monotonous harmonies in most pieces due to a combination of only C, F, and G and a bass line of almost all root notes.

Figure 7. Sample 14 with the chord model

Figure 8. Sample 14 with the non-chord model

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we report on our experiments with generating four-part harmonies for given soprano melodies by using Bayesian networks. Although related works have explicitly introduced to their machines the nodes or states that represent chords or harmonic functions, researchers should not explicitly introduce chords and nodes to the machine if they wish to determine whether the machine can acquire the principles of harmony from actual music data. Based on this idea, we attempted four-part harmonization with a Bayesian network that did not include chord nodes. The experimental results show that the non-chord model learned some basic rules in harmonics.

We suspect that machines take three steps while learning harmony: (1) avoiding dissonant notes, (2) avoiding prohibition in harmonics, and (3) exploring more musically aesthetic solutions. By reviewing the experimental results, we can see that our model without chord nodes attained the first step. To attain the second step (e.g., to avoid the prohibition of parallel 5th), our non-chord model will consider new dependencies, such as that between S_{i-1} and B_i . In

the future, we will advance our computational model by constructing a larger-scale corpus and by adding new dependencies.

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